

The role of state programs in the socio-economic development of greater Baku

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Abstract: The article investigates the impact of State Programs implemented between 2004 and 2023 on the socio-economic development of Greater Baku. The analysis shows that as a result of these programs, the economic potential of Baku has increased, the structure of industrial and service sectors has improved, and the number of newly created jobs has grown significantly. Statistical data indicate that during 2004–2023, the number of new jobs in Baku followed a steady upward trend, and the city's share in the national employment structure increased considerably. The implementation of the State Programs has also led to significant progress in the modernization of urban infrastructure, the improvement of social welfare, and the mitigation of environmental problems.

Keywords: *Greater Baku, socio-economic development, State Programs, employment, infrastructure, regional development*

Introduction. The State Programs adopted by Azerbaijan during the period of independence aim to ensure the country's development in economic, social, cultural, and other spheres. The socio-economic, ecological, and infrastructural development of Greater Baku is implemented within the framework of Azerbaijan's overall development strategy. State Programs serve as one of the main mechanisms for ensuring sustainable, balanced, and integrated urban growth. Since 2004, the consecutive State Programs have accelerated the development of both Baku and the regions, playing a key role in the formation of the non-oil sector, the expansion of services and other infrastructure areas, and the improvement of employment conditions.

The "State Program on the Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2004–2008)" laid the foundation for a new stage in this direction. In order to ensure the development of suburban settlements of Baku and to improve the living conditions of the population, the "State Program on the socio-economic development of Baku city and its settlements for 2006-2007" was adopted in 2006. Subsequently, a number of other programs, including the "State Program on the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2009-2013" the "State Program on the socio-economic development of Baku city and its settlements for 2011-2013" the "State Program on the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2014-2018" the "State Program on the socio-economic development of Baku city and its settlements for 2014-2016" and the "State Program on the socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2019-2023" were implemented. The implementation of these programs has had a significant impact on the socio-economic development of Baku.

Analysis and discussion. As a result of the implementation of the State Programs, the socio-economic development of Baku has accelerated over the past two decades. The aforementioned State Programs, covering areas such as the economy, employment, socio-cultural development, urban planning and infrastructure, and environmental sustainability, have ensured the comprehensive development of the city.

Within the framework of these programs, substantial efforts have been made to promote the socio-economic growth of Baku, establish production and service facilities in various sectors of the economy, and increase the level of employment among the population. During 2004-2008, 153180 new jobs were created in Baku, and during 2009-2013, 133583 new jobs were created, accounting for 30% and 37,3% of all new jobs established across the country, respectively. In 2014-2018, the number of newly created jobs increased compared to previous periods, reaching 38,4% of the national total, while in 2019-2023 this figure rose to 61,3% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of job creation during the implementation of State Programs

One of the main objectives in the adoption of State Programs is the diversification of the economy, particularly the development of the non-oil sector. In an era of rapidly globalizing world economy, reducing the country’s dependence on the oil sector, especially on extractive industries, has become a crucial issue. In this regard, significant attention has been paid to the development of light industry. In 2008, the “Prime Cotton” LLC Baku Textile Factory, equipped with modern technological machinery, was established to support this direction. The factory produces knitted and woven yarn from locally sourced raw materials (cotton fiber) and currently employs 112 workers. A large portion of its products is exported to foreign countries, including Russia, Belarus, Iran, Turkey, and others (Azerbaijan Employers Confederation, 2025)

In addition, Industrial Parks and Districts have been established in various cities and regions of the country. The Balakhani, Garadagh, and Pirallahi Industrial Parks created in Baku serve as notable examples. The Balakhani Industrial Park, founded in 2012, consists of enterprises engaged in waste recycling. The park’s activities are based on the application of modern technologies in industry, ensuring the sustainable and repeated use of natural resources. Currently, 27 resident companies operate within the park, providing more than 1,100 jobs (Ministry of Economy, 2025).

The Garadagh Industrial Park, established in 2015, is an area equipped with modern technological facilities designated for shipbuilding and planned future activities in other industrial sectors. Currently, one resident company—the “Baku Shipbuilding Plant” LLC—operates within the park, providing 758 jobs (Economic Zones Development Agency, 2025). The full-scale operation of this Industrial Park in the future is expected to play a key role in addressing employment challenges in the Garadagh administrative district, which is located far from the city center.

The Pirallahi Industrial Park was established in 2016 with the aim of developing the pharmaceutical industry and reducing the sector’s dependence on foreign markets. The park covers an area of 30 hectares. Although seven residents have been registered, currently two resident companies are in operation: “Diamed Co” LLC, which produces disposable syringes of various volumes, and “R-Pharm” LLC, which specializes in the production of pharmaceutical products. These enterprises together provide 555 jobs. In addition, work is underway to establish new facilities within the framework of projects such as the “Production of baby diapers” and “Production of jam and lemonade from saffron” (Economic Zones Development Agency, 2025).

One of the main priorities of the State Programs is the development of entrepreneurship in the city. In this direction, large-scale measures have been implemented. Since the beginning of the programs’ implementation, events on the theme “State Support for the Development of Entrepreneurship in Baku Settlements” have been organized, and technical assistance has been provided to 4,550 entrepreneurs in project selection and business plan preparation.

In the suburban settlements of Baku, concessional loans were provided to entrepreneurs with the support of the National Fund for Entrepreneurship Support. As a result, more than 5,300 new jobs were created. The financing of 53 projects based on the application of modern technologies was ensured, including 13 bread factories, 13 greenhouse complexes (covering an area of 48 hectares), 9 poultry farms, 2 meat processing plants, 2 metal construction enterprises, and 14 other industrial facilities. The commissioning of high-capacity factories has played an important role in strengthening food security and improving the food supply for the population living in Baku and its surrounding settlements.

Significant projects have been implemented in the suburban settlements of Baku with the aim of developing and modernizing agriculture. Modern greenhouse complexes have been established,

existing ones have been reconstructed, intensive horticultural farms have been created in the Zira settlement, and irrigation infrastructure for olive and almond orchards has been improved in the Khazar and Pirallahi districts.

As a result of the implementation of the State Programs, the establishment of modern industrial enterprises not only enhances the city's economic development but also plays an important role in addressing employment challenges and providing job opportunities for the urban population.

The State Programs also cover the development of social infrastructure and its establishment in accordance with modern standards. Significant projects have been implemented by the state to expand and improve healthcare and educational infrastructure. During the implementation period of the State Programs, major repair and reconstruction works were completed in 4 vocational schools, 174 general education schools, 121 kindergartens, and 3 creativity schools in Baku and its suburban settlements (State Program, 2019, p. 56).

In the state's social policy, the modernization of the healthcare sector and the protection of public health have been of particular importance. To improve the population's access to medical services, many hospitals, polyclinics, sanatoriums, and other medical institutions in the city have been either completely renovated or newly constructed. Within this framework, the construction of the National Health Center, a new hospital in the Badamdar settlement, the "City United Hospital No. 17" in Gobustan settlement, and the "City United Hospital No. 11" have been carried out. As a result of these measures, the strengthening of healthcare infrastructure has been ensured, the quality of modern medical services has improved, and efforts have been directed toward enhancing the population's health indicators (Socio-economic development of Baku, 2017, p. 85).

Extensive measures have also been implemented in the field of communications and information technologies. Eleven new automatic telephone exchanges (ATE) and nine post offices have been constructed, while the infrastructure of 28 ATE has been upgraded. In addition, fiber-optic cable lines have been installed in the Zira, Gurgan, and Pirallahi settlements, which has significantly expanded the technical capacity of Baku's internet network. As a result of these efforts, the access speed of "Bakinternet" to the global internet network has been increased (Socio-economic development of Baku, 2017).

Extensive measures have been implemented to repair and modernize the road and transport infrastructure in Baku city and its suburban settlements. For the purpose of optimizing the city's transport system, new bridges and tunnels have been constructed. A significant portion of the main highways connecting Baku's suburban settlements, as well as the internal road infrastructure, has been completely reconstructed. The renewal of the road infrastructure has been one of the main priorities within the framework of the State Program. For this purpose, major roads such as the Zabrat–Mashtaga–Buzovna highway, the road from "Zigh Circle" to the Gala station along the "Zigh roundabout–airport" route, the Zabrat–Kurdakhani–Pirshaghi road, the Bilgah–Novkhani–Sumgayit and Zigh–Hovsan roads, as well as the main road of the Bina settlement, have been completely rebuilt and opened to traffic. Inter-settlement roads have been thoroughly repaired, while asphalt covering has been laid on district and internal settlement roads. In addition, bridges, tunnels, and pedestrian crossings have been constructed and commissioned to ensure efficient traffic management and improve road safety.

In addition, the road and transport infrastructure of newly developed residential areas around the suburban settlements has been upgraded in accordance with modern standards. Within this framework, the roads leading to the "Badam Gardens" residential area from the Mardakan highway, the "Gosha Gishlag" residential area from the Pirallahi road, the "Savalan" residential area from the Zabrat–Mashtaga road, as well as the "Dairy State Farm" and "Bina Agrocomplex" residential areas from the Bina settlement, have been completely reconstructed and opened to traffic (State Program, 2019).

The suburban railway transport system of Baku has been restored. Since 2015, high-speed trains have been operating on the Baku–Pirshaghi–Sumgayit and Baku–Khirdalan routes. In the future, it is planned to further extend the railway lines and fully restore the former Baku circular railway line. The metro system, which plays a central role in urban passenger transportation, has also undergone major reconstruction, and new stations have been put into operation. The "Koroglu," "28 May," and "Icherisheher" stations have been completely renovated. New metro stations have been opened in 2008 ("Nasimi"), 2009 ("Azadlig Avenue"), 2011 ("Darnagul"), 2016 ("Avtovagzal" and "Akhmedli-2"), 2021 ("8 November"), and 2022 ("Khojasan"). These infrastructure projects have made a significant contribution to improving traffic safety, reducing transport congestion, and ensuring more efficient management of traffic flow within the city.

In 2009, the new “Baku International and Intercity Bus Terminal Complex,” fully equipped with modern infrastructure, was commissioned for public use in Baku. In 2014, the “New Terminal Complex” of the Heydar Aliyev International Airport was inaugurated. In the same year, to strengthen the city’s role in international freight transportation, the ferry terminal of the “Baku International Sea Trade Port” was opened in the Alat settlement. Located at the intersection of the modern Silk Road and major regional transport corridors, the port plays a key role in the country’s international cargo transportation network.

Significant measures have also been taken to improve the population’s access to public utilities, including electricity, gas, and water supply. To enhance the power supply system, new substations (Buzovna, AzDRAMA, Pirallahi, and Dubendi) have been constructed, while existing stations, power lines, and transformer substations have been reconstructed. High-voltage overhead and cable lines stretching for tens of kilometers have been renewed to ensure the reliable and stable operation of Baku’s energy network.

To improve the water supply and sewerage systems, substantial work has been carried out in the reconstruction of water distribution and sewage infrastructure across the city and its suburban settlements. Within the framework of the State Program, priority was given to areas with weak water supply. As a result, a total of 820 kilometers of water distribution networks have been constructed, and seven water reservoirs have been built in Baku and its surrounding settlements. At the same time, a 61-kilometer section of the “Jeyranbatan–Balakhani–Ramanah–Gala Main Water Pipeline” has been commissioned (State Program, 2018).

Significant projects have also been implemented in the field of sewerage infrastructure. A new sewerage network has been constructed, and sewerage collectors and pipelines have been cleaned using specialized equipment. These measures have played an important role in improving sanitary and hygienic conditions in the city. The construction of the Pirshaghi wastewater treatment facilities, the Darnagul–Bakikhanov–Garachukhur sewerage collector, and the Lokbatan–Khojasan sewerage tunnel has been completed, while the water supply and sewerage network within the framework of the “White City” project has been fully reconstructed (State Program, 2019).

Comprehensive measures have been implemented in Baku to preserve cultural heritage, protect historical and cultural monuments, and reconstruct and renovate cultural facilities. In this context, conservation and restoration works have been carried out on world-renowned architectural monuments such as the Icherisheher (Old City), the Maiden Tower, and the Shirvanshahs’ Palace Complex, aiming to preserve their original historical appearance and ensure their long-term protection.

In addition, a number of other historical buildings and mosques located in Baku have been restored and adapted to meet modern standards. Within the framework of cultural heritage protection, large-scale landscaping and improvement works have been conducted in the territory of the Icherisheher State Historical-Architectural Reserve, focusing on the preservation of historical residential quarters and the enhancement of their infrastructure.

In addition, several new parks and public recreation areas have been established in Baku to provide the urban population with better opportunities for leisure and recreation, while existing parks have been reconstructed. Within the framework of renovation projects, the “Baku Zoological Park,” the “Chemberekend Park,” and others have been modernized in accordance with contemporary ecosystem standards. These initiatives contribute to the transmission of national cultural heritage to future generations, the improvement of the ecological environment, and the enhancement of Baku’s tourism potential.

Conclusion. State Programs play a strategic role in the socio-economic development of Greater Baku. Within the framework of these programs, large-scale infrastructure projects have been implemented in the capital, leading to significant progress in improving social welfare, accelerating economic growth, and addressing environmental challenges. The State Programs have been instrumental in ensuring the sustainable development of Baku, regulating urbanization processes, and enhancing the overall socio-economic potential of the region.

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